

INFORMATION CULTURE: MODERN INTERPRETATION

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Abstract: The article analyzes the development stages of information culture. Also, the importance of forming information culture among young people in today's global processes is justified.

Keywords Information, intellectual potential, globalization, political, communication, radicalism, liberalism, information exchange, social phenomenon.

It is necessary to take into account concrete mental (level of intellectual potential and socio-professional) characteristics of people specific to the historical time and social space when studying the trends and laws of integration and differentiation of the interrelated areas of information culture. Because the theory of modeling and forecasting of the globalization of information culture requires knowledge of the laws of functional integration of scientific-research institutes, design organizations, engineering-technical and other areas of social activity in optimizing the interaction of the elements of the "nature-society-human-engineering-technology" system.

Accordingly, the main requirement of the current period is the constructive-rational organization of the communicative-integrative function of modeling and forecasting the globalization of information culture and the integration of inter-national spiritual-cultural relations. Because "spirituality", which is the attributive core of any civilization, is a continuous process that is always replenished. It continues to change and improve in an integral dialectical relationship with the changing times, its necessary demands and needs. Spirituality is a process in continuous motion. Just as thought, thinking, and feeling do not stop, spirituality, as their product, is always changing and renewing" [1].

The creative development and assimilation of the global information culture values and progressive traditions of the peoples of the world was manifested as its main principle and legitimacy. After all, when talking about the consequences of the globalization of civilizations, the integration of spiritual relations - the universality of human culture creates such a basis around which all directions of social activity crystallize [2]. This, in turn, is an opportunity to assess the process of globalization of information culture, the directions of integration of national and universal values, the positive or negative character of its consequences and forecast the impact.

The need for the globalization of information culture and the integration of international spiritual and cultural relations determines the need to model the strategic directions and tactical tasks of cooperation in the social, economic, and political spheres of humanity, but the fact that all countries in the world do not follow the universal principles of the globalization of information culture equally, absolutize their ethno-egoistic and egocentric interests, leading to alternative models and forecasts.

In such conditions, it is important to ensure the mutual harmony of the "need-goal-interest-method-means-result" system in the globalization of information culture, but if the positive and negative consequences of the globalization of information culture are not analyzed in the context of the relationship between the elements of this system, their existence and

development trends neither accurate modeling nor forecasting is possible. Because the globalization paradigms of information culture are constantly changing and developing, they do not meet the generally accepted and practically existing standards. This, in turn, shows the crucial importance of interstate dialogues regarding the globalization of civilizations in general, and the globalization of information culture in particular [3].

The mutual cooperation of countries in the process of global information culture integration (even in the conditions of priority of individuality in the identification of their models) is a condition for coordinating the development of their national information culture with universal laws, but since integration into the global information culture is a continuous (permanent) process, the national development models of different countries in this field, as well as their it should be considered in internal unity, correlation relationship.

Otherwise, the concepts of nationalism and universality, traditionalism and modernity, sociality and individuality, passivity and activity in the integration models of the global information culture are limited within the specific interests of individuals or social units (even if they are used to determine the status and role of states in this process), the fundamental nature of the development of events does not represent

Because the modeling and forecasting of the above-mentioned events is conditional and relative according to the characteristics of the social space and historical time, but if the problem is approached in the context of a concrete person's activity, regardless of the level of his awareness, socio-political activity, intellectual potential, and cultural level, integration into global processes should be considered as the object and subject of the model.

The function of modeling and forecasting the development of information culture in general, and in particular the process of integration into it, is to learn from historical experiences, identify negative consequences and directions of influence that are likely to occur, and prevent them. In this case, ensuring the "spiritual-ideological immunity" of individuals and society to "pathological civilization" (more precisely, to its "anomalous state"), especially social-psychological alienation[4].

After all, the functional differentiation of modern global science in the matter of information culture also represents the process of integration of different areas of scientific knowledge. After all, these processes show the general laws of globalization of information culture and become a rational-constructive theoretical-methodological basis for the global organization, management and control of the proportionality of the interaction of the elements of the "nature-society-man-technique-technology" system.

Therefore, a complex-systemic approach to the nature of the problem requires a relatively perfect system of criteria for evaluating events. Artificially forced politicization and ideologization of the consequences of information culture, only to the character of the political, economic, ideological structure of society, to the interests of certain social strata, leads to absurd conclusions.

In other words, on the one hand, the objectivity and effectiveness of modeling and forecasting the development of information culture - to the level of development of the social-political, technical-technological, spiritual-cultural foundations of society; on the other hand, the effectiveness of scientific modeling of the process of integration of states into the field of information culture depends on the citizens' knowledge of the laws of socio-economic,

political-cultural, spiritual-ethical sustainable development of the society and their use in their practical activities.

References:

1. И.А Биз келажакимизни ўз қўлимиз билан қураимиз. 7 – том. –Тошкент, Ўзбекистон НМИУ, 1999. 302 б.
2. Хантингтон С. Столкновение цивилизаций. Пер. с англ. Т. Велимеева. Ю. Новикова. — Москва: ООО «Издательство АСТ», 2003. – С. 409.
3. охраним ли человечество человечность?: Доклад Независимой комиссии по международным гуманитарным вопросам. - Москва, 1989 .С. 241.
4. И.А Биз келажакимизни ўз қўлимиз билан қураимиз. 7 – том. –Тошкент, Ўзбекистон НМИУ, 1999. 302 б.